

THE YEMEN CRISIS, RED SEA SECURITY AND ROLE OF EXTERNAL FORCES: NAVIGATING THE PROSPECT

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Abstract:

This paper examines the complex dynamics of the ongoing Yemen war and its profound implications for Red Sea security. Since the conflict's onset in 2015, Yemen has been at the centre of a devastating civil war, drawing in regional powers like Saudi Arabia and Iran, which has fuelled sectarian tensions and destabilized the broader Middle East. Yemen's strategic location along the Bab al-Mandab Strait, a critical chokepoint for global maritime trade, has intensified concerns about Red Sea security. Houthi forces have frequently targeted vessels and infrastructure tied to international shipping routes, further compounding risks. Tensions have risen even higher following Hamas's October 2023 attack on Israel, which has engaged additional countries with various strategic interests. The Yemen conflict has significantly disrupted Red Sea security, impacted trade, and raised the potential for broader regional confrontation.

Through an analysis of military involvement and diplomatic efforts, this research explores the roles of Saudi Arabia, Iran, the United States, European Union, and United Nations in attempting to contain the violence. Focusing on regional and international security frameworks, the study assesses the critical challenges posed by the Yemen war to Red Sea security and explores avenues for conflict resolution.

Keyword:

Research Questions

1. How has the Yemen war, particularly the involvement of Houthi forces, affected the security of the Red Sea and surrounding regions?
2. What are the primary threats to Red Sea maritime routes due to the Yemen conflict, and how have they evolved since 2015?
3. What opportunities exist for resolving the Yemen conflict, and how can enhanced security cooperation in the Red Sea region facilitate long-term stability?

Objectives

1. To analyse the security threats arising from the Yemen war, emphasizing Houthi maritime tactics and their impact on Red Sea shipping and trade.
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of regional and international security responses to the conflict.
3. To explore potential avenues for conflict resolution, focusing on multilateral cooperation and security arrangements in the Red Sea region.

By examining the broader trajectory of the Yemen conflict rather than isolated incidents, this paper provides a comprehensive analysis of how the war has reshaped regional security dynamics. It aims to identify both the challenges and opportunities for fostering long-term peace in Yemen while securing one of the world's most crucial maritime zones. Utilizing secondary sources, including reports from international security organizations, the study underscores the urgency of addressing the conflict's spillover effects on global trade and regional stability.

1. Introduction

The Red Sea is one of the world's most strategically significant waterways, serving as a critical link between Europe and Asia, connecting the Mediterranean Sea to the Indian Ocean through the Suez Canal and the Bab el-Mandeb Strait. This geographical location has endowed the Red Sea with immense geopolitical value, particularly in the context of global trade, energy transportation, and military power projection. (Alexandre, 2021)Historically, it has been a focal point for empires, colonial powers, and regional actors seeking to control

maritime routes and assert dominance in the broader Middle East and Horn of Africa.

In recent decades, the Red Sea has taken on even greater significance due to several factors, including the discovery of vast natural resources in the surrounding regions, the rise of global economic interdependence, and increasing military competition among both regional and global powers. The vulnerability of strategic chokepoints, such as the Bab el-Mandeb Strait, which lies at the southern entrance of the Red Sea, has made it a flashpoint for conflicts and crises. This chokepoint is essential for the flow of oil and goods between Europe, the Middle East, and Asia, with approximately 6.2 million barrels of oil passing through the Bab el-Mandeb daily, making it a lifeline for energy supplies. Disruptions in this region can have severe economic and political consequences for both regional states and major global powers reliant on secure maritime transportation routes. Winslow (2001)

The ongoing Yemen War, which erupted in 2015, has exacerbated the already volatile geopolitical landscape of the Red Sea. Yemen's position along the southern coastline of the Red Sea makes it a critical player in maritime security. As the war has escalated, the country's ports, such as Hudaydah and Aden, have become contested areas of control between the internationally recognized Yemeni government, Houthi rebels, and various external actors. (Lubczynski & Matusitz, 2024) The involvement of regional powers such as Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates (UAE) in the conflict has further complicated the dynamics of the Red Sea. These countries, backed by their Western allies, view the conflict as a battleground for broader regional power struggles, particularly against Iran, which supports the Houthi rebels. For Saudi Arabia and the UAE, control over the Red Sea's maritime routes is crucial to safeguarding their economic interests and ensuring the security of oil exports. (Charles W. Dunne, 2023)

The geopolitical importance of the Red Sea has attracted the attention of global powers such as the United States, China, and Russia. These actors have strategic military and economic interests in the region and have established a growing naval presence. The U.S. Navy's Fifth Fleet, for instance, regularly patrols the Red Sea to protect international shipping lanes and maintain regional stability. (Mishra & Gurjar, 2022) Meanwhile, China, through its Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), has

invested heavily in infrastructure projects in countries bordering the Red Sea, such as Djibouti, where it has established its first overseas military base. Russia has also sought to expand its influence in the region, seeking alliances with Red Sea littoral states and exploring opportunities for naval basing rights.(MacBride & Chatzky, 2020)

This paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the maritime geopolitics of the Red Sea, focusing on how the region's strategic significance is intertwined with the Yemen War and the involvement of external forces. By examining the complex interplay between local, regional, and global actors, this study will explore how the Red Sea Crisis has emerged as a conflict nexus, with the potential to impact global trade, energy security, and regional stability. The paper also aims to shed light on the motivations behind external interventions in the Yemen War, from Saudi Arabia's efforts to maintain regional dominance to Iran's strategy of expanding its influence through proxy warfare. Ultimately, this research seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of the Red Sea as a theatre of maritime competition and its role in shaping contemporary geopolitical dynamics.

2. Literature Review

The strategic importance of the Red Sea has been extensively analysed in various scholarly works, particularly due to its role as a major maritime route critical to global trade and energy flows. The Red Sea's geographical position, bordering Africa and the Arabian Peninsula, places it at the crossroads of multiple regions and trade routes. This has led scholars such as (Woever, 2003) to apply the concept of **regional security complexes** to the Red Sea, where interdependence and geographic proximity between states generate unique security challenges. According to this framework, the Red Sea represents a regional security complex in which both local and external actors' competing interests intensify security dilemmas, affecting the region's overall stability. The ongoing competition between Saudi Arabia, Iran, and other external actors, driven by concerns over resource control, influence, and security, is emblematic of this theory.

In the specific context of the Yemen War, sectarianism and proxy warfare have emerged as dominant themes in academic discourse. (Gause, 2014) argues that the Sunni-Shia divide, particularly between Saudi Arabia and Iran, has deepened the conflict in Yemen. The war has

turned into a proxy battleground where regional actors back opposing factions to project power and counterbalance their rivals. This proxy warfare has broader implications for the Red Sea region, as Iran supports the Houthi rebels to gain influence over maritime chokepoints, while Saudi Arabia and the UAE seek to counter Iran's influence to protect their trade routes and security.

Critical geopolitics is another lens through which scholars have examined the Red Sea's strategic significance. (Derrick Sidaway, 1997) and others have explored how geography is not just a physical landscape but also a tool of political power. States use geography to assert dominance, control resources, and influence regional or global dynamics. In the case of the Red Sea, control over key maritime chokepoints like the Bab el-Mandeb Strait has become a strategic goal for global powers such as the United States, China, and Russia, each looking to expand their influence through military presence, naval bases, or alliances with littoral states. This geopolitical competition in the Red Sea reflects a broader global contest for influence in critical maritime spaces, as states recognize the importance of controlling strategic waterways to secure their economic and military interests.

The existing literature underscores the Red Sea's status as a region of immense geopolitical and strategic importance, shaped by the interplay of local conflicts, such as the Yemen War, and the broader geopolitical interests of regional and global powers. The region's security dynamics are defined by a combination of sectarian divisions, proxy warfare, and the strategic use of geography, making it a crucial area of study for understanding the intersection of maritime geopolitics and conflict.

3. Conceptual Framework

The relationship between maritime geopolitics, the Red Sea Crisis, and the Yemen War centers on strategic chokepoints, proxy warfare, economic and security interests, and international law. The Bab el-Mandeb Strait, connecting the Indian Ocean to the Mediterranean via the Suez Canal, is a critical chokepoint for global trade, especially for oil and gas supplies. (U.S. Department of Energy, 2024) Its vulnerability was evident when Houthi forces, backed by Iran, attacked Saudi oil tankers, prompting Saudi Arabia to temporarily halt shipments through the strait. (EIA, 2023) Control over this chokepoint is central to the

conflict, with Saudi Arabia and the UAE aiming to safeguard their economic and security interests.

The Yemen War is often described as a proxy conflict, where Iran supports the Houthis to extend its influence in the Red Sea, while Saudi Arabia and its coalition partners work to counter Iran's regional ambitions (Juneau, 2016) The Red Sea's significance extends beyond the immediate conflict, drawing global powers like the U.S. and China, both of which have established military presences in the region. (Allard, n.d.) The UAE has further solidified its position by developing military bases and port infrastructure along the Red Sea coast, highlighting the strategic importance of this maritime route for regional stability. (Katzman, 2011)

Maritime security is a growing concern, particularly regarding the enforcement of international law. The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) outlines maritime rights and responsibilities, but ongoing conflict challenges its enforcement. Efforts by multinational coalitions, such as the Combined Maritime Forces (CMF), have sought to mitigate piracy and secure shipping lanes, though conflicting interests among regional and global actors have complicated these initiatives. (United Nations Security Council, 2020)The role of international organizations, including the United Nations, in mediating peace and maintaining security remains crucial, but their effectiveness has been limited by the persistence of hostilities.(Navigating the Red Sea: Addressing Threats and Harnessing Potential | SIPRI, n.d.)

4. Analysis

The Red Sea Crisis and the Yemen War have become critical issues that resonate deeply in today's world, affecting the lives of millions and altering regional dynamics. The Red Sea, a vital waterway for global trade, plays a key role in this unfolding drama, while the conflict in Yemen reveals the human cost of geopolitical struggles. As external forces shape the course of events, this analysis seeks to shed light on how these interconnected challenges influence not just politics, but the everyday lives of those caught in the crossfire. By weaving together facts and theories, we can better understand the complexities and human impact of this crisis.

I. Strategic Significance of the Red Sea

The Red Sea holds immense geopolitical and economic importance as a key maritime route for global trade and energy supplies. Its strategic value is magnified by its location, linking the Mediterranean Sea to the Indian Ocean through the Bab el-Mandeb Strait and the Suez Canal. These two chokepoints are essential not only for regional commerce but also for global maritime traffic, including oil, gas, and other critical goods.(Jun Qiao; Mingxuan Huang; Yitong Li, n.d.) The following points delve into the specifics of this significance:

A. The Bab el-Mandeb Strait: A Crucial Maritime Chokepoint

The Bab el-Mandeb Strait, positioned at the southern tip of the Red Sea, is one of the world's most critical maritime chokepoints. Roughly 6.2 million barrels of oil, or about 9% of the world's total seaborne oil trade, pass through this narrow waterway every day, demonstrating its strategic relevance to global energy markets. A blockage or disruption in this strait could cause significant supply chain disruptions, leading to spikes in global oil prices, as witnessed in past conflicts. The Bab el-Mandeb Strait is not only vital for oil shipments but also for the transit of liquefied natural gas (LNG) and other bulk goods.(U.S. Department of Energy, 2024)

The strait connects the Red Sea with the Gulf of Aden and, by extension, the Arabian Sea and Indian Ocean, forming a direct link between Europe, the Middle East, and South Asia. It serves as a faster and more cost-effective route for ships traveling between Europe and Asia compared to alternative paths like rounding the Cape of Good Hope at the southern tip of Africa.(Gurjar, 2024)

B. The Suez Canal: A Global Trade Artery

The Suez Canal, located at the northern end of the Red Sea, amplifies the region's strategic importance. Opened in 1869, the canal revolutionized global maritime trade by providing a direct route between the Mediterranean Sea and the Indian Ocean, significantly reducing the time and cost of transporting goods between Europe and Asia. The canal's role in bypassing the lengthy journey around Africa makes it indispensable for international shipping.(Shumilov & Malova, 2024)

As of 2023, over 50 ships passed through the Suez Canal daily, carrying approximately 12% of global trade, including oil, consumer goods, and military equipment. This figure underscores the canal's vital role in

sustaining the interconnectedness of the global economy. Moreover, disruptions in the Suez Canal can lead to massive backlogs, as seen during the Ever-Given incident in 2021, which caused a global shipping crisis and resulted in billions of dollars in economic losses.(The New Zealand Embassy in Cairo., n.d.)

The region's infrastructure has further enhanced its importance. For example, the Suez Canal Economic Zone has attracted billions of dollars in foreign investment, with China alone committing \$8 billion to develop logistics hubs and manufacturing zones. These investments underscore the economic stakes in ensuring the security and stability of the Red Sea and its surrounding waterways.(Rakha & El-Aasar, 2024)

C. Military and Geopolitical Significance

Beyond its economic importance, the Red Sea also holds considerable military significance. It serves as a vital maritime corridor for naval deployments and military logistics for powers such as the United States, China, Russia, and regional actors like Saudi Arabia and Egypt. The presence of foreign military bases in countries bordering the Red Sea, such as Djibouti, underscores the strategic military competition in the region. Djibouti, for instance, hosts bases for the US, China, France, and Japan, highlighting the Red Sea's critical role in global military strategies, especially in the fight against piracy, terrorism, and ensuring the safety of maritime trade route.(Center for International Maritime Security, n.d.)

Control over the Red Sea and its strategic waterways holds critical importance for states like Egypt and Saudi Arabia, both in terms of national security and regional hegemony. For Egypt, the Red Sea's significance is tied to its control over the Suez Canal, a vital maritime chokepoint that facilitates a significant portion of global trade and generates essential revenue for the Egyptian economy. The canal's uninterrupted operation is a core element of Egypt's economic security, elevating the strategic importance of maintaining security and stability in the Red Sea.(Sajeev & Costa, 2024)

For Saudi Arabia, the Red Sea serves as a critical maritime axis, connecting its key urban centers and ports, such as Jeddah, to international markets. The waterway supports Saudi Arabia's economic lifeline, particularly in terms of energy exports and trade flows, while also reinforcing the kingdom's geopolitical standing within the region.

The Red Sea thus becomes indispensable for both states, not only as an economic artery but also as a platform to project influence and safeguard national interests.(Mukherjee, 2024)

From a broader security perspective, the Red Sea is a vital zone for naval operations and foreign military interventions. It provides a critical route for military patrols, as well as a staging ground for the projection of naval power by external actors, particularly in times of regional conflict. For external powers, such as the United States, European Union, and other international stakeholders, the Red Sea serves as a forward operating area where naval deployments ensure the balance of power and protect strategic interests in the Middle East. These forces provide logistical support, deterrence, and rapid response capabilities to assist regional allies, thereby reinforcing the security architecture of the region.(Frederic Gateretse-Ngoga, 2024)

The geopolitical importance of the Red Sea, therefore, extends far beyond its economic value. It is a contested space where regional and international actors vie for influence, making it a focal point for power projection and security dynamics in the broader Middle East. In the context of ongoing conflicts, particularly the Yemen crisis, control and security of the Red Sea are integral to the strategic calculations of regional and global powers alike.(Dunne, 2021)

II. Impact of the Yemen War on Maritime Security

The Yemen War, which erupted in 2015, has severely destabilized the Red Sea region, posing significant threats to maritime security, particularly due to the activities of the Iran-backed Houthi rebels. As a consequence, the Red Sea, especially the Bab el-Mandeb Strait, has become a focal point for both local and international security concerns, with heightened risks to global shipping and energy supplies.(Pradhan, 2024)

a) Houthi Threats to Shipping Routes

One of the most significant consequences of the Yemen conflict has been the Houthis' targeting of international shipping routes in the Red Sea. The Houthis, whose strongholds are near the Yemeni coast, have frequently threatened and attacked vessels transiting the region, including oil tankers and cargo ships. Their ability to launch missile and drone attacks on ships has increased with support from Iran, whose provision of sophisticated weapons systems was documented in a 2020

UN report. This has introduced unprecedented risks for global maritime trade.(Kuoman, 2024)

One notable incident occurred in November 2018, when Houthi forces attacked two Saudi oil tankers in the Red Sea. In response, Saudi Arabia temporarily suspended oil shipments through the Bab el-Mandeb Strait, underscoring the vulnerability of this chokepoint. The temporary suspension highlighted the ripple effects that disruptions in this critical waterway can have on global oil supplies, causing instability in oil markets and raising concerns about energy security.(Jazeera, 2018)

The recent surge in attacks, particularly since the escalation of the Gaza war in October 2023, reflects a significant shift in the Houthis' strategy, using the conflict as an opportunity to assert their influence and leverage in the region. These attacks have predominantly targeted vessels linked to Israel and its allies, underscoring the Houthis' growing military capabilities and their intent to disrupt maritime security in the Red Sea.(Carlson, 2024)

The Houthis have increasingly relied on long-range missiles, not only to strike at targets within Israel but also to threaten critical maritime routes in the Red Sea. This development has heightened concerns among regional and international actors, as the group's enhanced military capacity poses a considerable threat to both shipping lanes and the broader security architecture of the region. The rise in Houthi maritime operations represents a broader pattern of militarization, signaling their intent to challenge regional power dynamics and complicate the strategic calculations of external powers operating in the Red Sea and surrounding areas.(Kaushal, 2024)

b) Escalation of Maritime Insecurity

The maritime insecurity in the Red Sea extends beyond oil. According to a 2019 report by the International Maritime Organization (IMO), there were numerous incidents involving threats or direct attacks on commercial vessels in the region, with many of these attributed to the ongoing conflict in Yemen. The report identified attacks by both the Houthis and other non-state actors, including pirate groups exploiting the region's instability.(International Maritime Organization (IMO), 2019)

The conflict has resulted in a significant increase in insurance premiums for ships operating in or near the Red Sea, as vessels now face higher

risks of attack or disruption. This, in turn, has raised the cost of shipping through the region, with global economic repercussions. For example, premiums for vessels passing through the Bab el-Mandeb Strait skyrocketed after the 2018 attacks, adding further financial strain on international shipping companies.(Denamiel et al., 2024)

Table 1: Houthi Maritime Attacks Post-19 October 2023

The table below provides a detailed chronology of Houthi maritime attacks post-19 October 2023, illustrating the evolution of their strategies and operational impact.

Date/Period	Details	Impact
19 October 2023	Initial attacks began, targeting southern Israel with long-range missiles and drones.	Mostly unsuccessful long-range attacks.
November 2023	Shift to targeting Israeli-linked vessels closer to Yemen in the southern Red Sea.	Increased targeting of vessels with Israeli connections.
December 2023	Declared all vessels heading to Israel as military targets; began operations in Bab al-Mandab.	Expanded target range and operational area.
9 January 2024	Start of the fourth phase marked by the Houthis claiming their first attack on a US warship.	Marked the start of the fourth phase.
Early 2024	First round of US-led strikes on Houthi military assets in Yemen.	Escalated conflict; US intervention began.
January - March 2024	16 attacks on ships with ties to US- and UK-based owners/operators; notable attacks included sinking of the Rubymar.	Significant increase in attacks on commercial vessels.
6 March 2024	Attack on the Barbadian-flagged, Liberian-owned bulk carrier True Confidence resulted in three fatalities.	Deadliest attack since the escalation began.
Mid-February 2024	Peak activity with 27 attacks, almost as many as the first two phases combined.	Highest activity level recorded to date.
17 February 2024	US designation of the Houthis as a Specially Designated Global Terrorist (SDGT) group.	Triggered increased Houthi retaliatory actions.
2 February	Resumption of attacks on Israeli-	Intermittent attacks on

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2024	linked vessels intermittently.	Israeli targets resumed.
March - April 2024	Expansion into the Gulf of Aden; significant drop in attacks toward Israel.	Expanded operational area; decreased attacks on Israeli targets.
4 January 2024	The Behshad moved from Red Sea to Gulf of Aden; later targeted in a US cyberattack and withdrawn to Djibouti Port.	Temporary reduction in attack effectiveness.
4 April 2024	The Behshad set sail for Iran; coincided with Israeli bombing of Iranian consulate and upcoming Iranian attacks on Israel.	Temporary de-escalation in Houthi attacks.
27 April 2024	First claimed attack deep into the Indian Ocean, marking the start of the next phase.	Start of a new phase with expanded operational range.
April 2024	Fewest attacks since October, with only one successful attack in April compared to 13 in January and February.	Fewest attacks recorded; decreased operational tempo.
Source: Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project (ACLED, 2024b)		

As illustrated in the table, the evolution of Houthi maritime attacks reflects a complex interplay of strategic adjustments and regional dynamics. The data shows a shift from initial unsuccessful long-range strikes to a more focused and impactful series of attacks targeting vessels with connections to the US, UK, and Israel. The peak activity in mid-February and the subsequent de-escalation highlights the volatile nature of the conflict and the influence of broader geopolitical events.

Figure I. Maritime Incidents and Responses as of September 6, 2024

Source: CRS, using U.S. government statements and media reports.

Note: Attack incidents involving multiple targets may be considered a single incident. Unreported/unacknowledged incidents not reflected. Data approximate and subject to revision.

Additionally, naval patrols by international coalitions have increased to safeguard maritime routes, particularly around the Bab el-Mandeb. The US Navy, along with allies from Europe and the Gulf, has intensified its presence in the region, conducting surveillance and anti-piracy operations to mitigate threats from the Houthis and other groups. However, despite these efforts, the persistent instability in Yemen continues to pose serious risks to maritime security, impacting not just regional actors but also the broader global trade network.

c) Economic and Strategic Repercussions

The Yemen conflict has had a significant economic impact on global trade, particularly due to disruptions in key shipping routes through the Red Sea. These interruptions lead to delays in the delivery of goods, higher shipping costs, and increased uncertainty in supply chains. Countries and corporations dependent on the steady flow of oil, gas, and other goods through the Suez Canal and Bab el-Mandeb are especially affected. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), such disruptions caused a 10% spike in global oil prices, illustrating the vulnerability of oil markets to any disturbance in major maritime chokepoints. Even a brief closure of the Bab el-Mandeb could result in

severe supply shortages, forcing oil tankers to take longer and more costly routes around the Cape of Good Hope.(IMF, 2024)

These disruptions would not only increase transportation costs but could also raise consumer prices and trigger economic instability in oil-dependent nations. This highlights the critical need for stability in the Red Sea to ensure the uninterrupted flow of oil and other goods, underscoring the region's economic importance in global geopolitics.(IMF, 2020)

Furthermore, prolonged disruptions in the Red Sea could significantly impact global energy markets. Rerouting oil tankers and other vessels around the Cape of Good Hope would add substantial time and cost to shipping operations, driving up oil prices and leading to a ripple effect on the prices of consumer goods and industrial inputs worldwide.

The growing risk of maritime conflict in the Red Sea reflects deeper geopolitical dynamics. Iran's support for the Houthi rebels in Yemen represents a strategic challenge to Saudi Arabia and its coalition partners, turning the conflict into a proxy war between regional powers. This instability not only affects Middle Eastern security but also has broader consequences for the global economy, making the Red Sea a critical region in both trade and international geopolitics.(Global Conflict Tracker, 2024)

III. Role of External Forces

The geopolitical landscape of the Red Sea region, shaped by external forces in the Yemen War, exposes broader rivalries, contradictions, and strategic interests. As Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Iran, China, and the US engage in a multi-layered struggle for regional dominance, the consequences for global trade, security, and diplomacy are profound. The ongoing war in Gaza and the Houthis' escalation of attacks on Red Sea shipping routes further complicate this picture, testing the limits of influence exerted by global powers like China and the US.

a) Saudi Arabia and the UAE: Securing Regional Influence through Military and Economic Investments

Saudi Arabia's involvement in Yemen reflects its ambition to maintain dominance in the Arabian Peninsula and secure its southern borders. Leading the Arab coalition against Iran-backed Houthi rebels, Saudi

Arabia has invested heavily in this conflict, dedicating 7.4% of its GDP to defence in 2022—making it the world’s second-largest spender relative to GDP and fifth in total defence spending at \$75 billion. Its military efforts include airstrikes, naval blockades, and the establishment of military bases along the Yemeni coastline and in nearby countries like Eritrea and Djibouti. These bases provide a strategic advantage by positioning Saudi forces near vital maritime routes, enabling control over the Bab el-Mandeb Strait and the Red Sea's shipping lanes.(Group, 2023)

The UAE's involvement in South Yemen is deeply rooted in both strategic and ideological interests. Since the outbreak of the Yemen war in 2015, the UAE has played a critical role in the Southern Transitional Council (STC), a separatist group that seeks to establish an independent state in South Yemen. The UAE has provided financial, military, and political support to the STC, thereby consolidating its influence in key areas such as Aden and Socotra.(ACLED, 2024a)

In addition to backing the STC, the UAE has sought to develop and control key infrastructure projects, including ports and airports in the south. The port of Aden, in particular, is seen as a vital asset for the UAE, as it enhances the country's ability to project power across the Arabian Sea and into the Horn of Africa. Socotra Island, strategically located at the crossroads of major shipping routes, has also been a focal point of Emirati interest, as the UAE has developed military bases and expanded its logistical footprint there.(Baabood, 2023)

By aligning itself with southern forces in Yemen, the UAE not only counters the influence of the Houthi movement, which controls much of northern Yemen, but also strengthens its broader maritime strategy across the Red Sea and the Gulf of Aden. This involvement allows the UAE to secure critical maritime choke points, including the Bab el-Mandeb Strait, a key artery for global trade. Furthermore, the UAE's role in South Yemen provides it with leverage in international negotiations, positioning it as a central actor in the geopolitics of both the Arabian Peninsula and the Horn of Africa.(Baabood, 2023)

b) Iran: Proxy Warfare as a Strategic Tool for Regional Influence

Iran’s support for the Houthi rebels is a calculated effort to challenge Saudi and UAE influence in Yemen while extending its strategic reach into the Arabian Peninsula. According to a 2020 United Nations report,

Iranian-made ballistic missiles and drones have been supplied to the Houthis, enabling them to target Saudi and Emirati assets. This proxy warfare strategy allows Iran to exert control without direct military involvement, weakening Saudi Arabia and creating leverage over one of the world's most vital waterways.(U.S. Mission to Yemen, 2024)

The Red Sea's strategic importance to global trade cannot be overstated. Approximately 6.2 million barrels of oil pass through the Bab el-Mandeb Strait daily. By aiding the Houthis in disrupting shipping routes, Iran undermines Saudi control and exerts influence over global oil markets, a critical concern for the world economy. This draws not only regional actors but also major global powers like the US and China into the conflict, given the economic stakes involved.(Perkins, 2023)

c) China and the US: Geopolitical Contradictions and Strategic Interests in the Red Sea

The recent Houthi attacks on Red Sea shipping routes have placed China in a difficult position, highlighting the contradictions in international expectations placed on Beijing and Washington's own diplomatic inaction. At the outset of Israel's military offensive in Gaza, China stood alongside Saudi Arabia and Iran in condemning Israeli aggression, calling for a negotiated settlement that addresses Palestinian grievances. However, the Houthis' escalation in the Red Sea has fractured this regional consensus, leaving China to navigate complex diplomatic waters.(Scott, 2024)

As the world's largest exporter and a key player in global shipping, China has a significant economic stake in the stability of the Red Sea region. More than 60% of its exports to Europe pass through the Suez Canal, and Chinese companies have recently invested \$8 billion in the Suez Canal Economic Zone. Despite assurances from the Houthis that Chinese vessels will not be targeted unless bound for Israel, the disruption in shipping routes has caused economic damage, with delays and losses affecting Chinese manufacturers.(K, 2024)

China's reaction has been cautious. While avoiding direct condemnation of the Houthis or public linkage to Iran, Chinese officials have repeatedly called for the protection of navigation and respect for international shipping routes. The US, however, has sought to pressure China to use its influence over Iran to halt the Houthi attacks. Despite

this, China's actual leverage over Iran appears limited. While China is Iran's largest trading partner and a major purchaser of Iranian oil, much of these purchases are made by private refineries operating outside official state channels to avoid US sanctions.(Scott, 2024)

Moreover, while China has committed to long-term investment projects in Iran, these ventures have often stalled. Iran lags behind other Middle Eastern nations in attracting Chinese foreign direct investment. Therefore, despite strong economic ties, China's ability to convert its influence into meaningful leverage over Iran is constrained.

d) The Limits of Chinese Influence and Washington's Contradictory Approach

Although China is being urged to intervene in the Red Sea crisis, Washington's demands reveal contradictions in its own foreign policy. The US has substantial influence over Israel, providing it with \$3.8 billion annually in military aid. Yet, despite this considerable leverage, the US has been reluctant to push Israel toward de-escalation in Gaza. Instead, Washington continues to send arms to Israel, fueling the conflict while pressing China to restrain Iran and the Houthis.(Lons, n.d.)

The US has repeatedly asked China to intervene with Iran, suggesting that Beijing has an "obligation" to use its influence to end the Red Sea crisis. Yet, Washington's unwillingness to use its own considerable influence over Israel to curb its military campaign in Gaza exposes a double standard. The US has far greater leverage over Israel than China has over Iran, and yet it continues to pursue a military solution in Gaza while expecting diplomatic results from China in the Red Sea.(K, 2024)

Conclusion

The Yemen War and the Red Sea crisis illustrate how local conflicts are intertwined with broader global rivalries. Saudi Arabia, the UAE, and Iran are engaged in power struggles that reflect their respective ambitions to control strategic maritime routes and regional influence. Meanwhile, global powers like China and the US are drawn into these conflicts not only because of diplomatic alliances but also due to critical economic interests, particularly in maintaining the security of global trade routes.(Baabood, 2023)

The contradictions in Washington's approach, demanding Chinese intervention while refusing to use its own influence over Israel, highlight the complexities of modern geopolitics. With the Red Sea representing a crucial artery for global trade, the stakes for both regional and global actors are enormous. Without a concerted effort to address the grievances driving these conflicts and the broader geopolitical ambitions of external forces, the crises in Yemen, Gaza, and the Red Sea are likely to continue, with potentially far-reaching consequences for international security and economic stability.

The Red Sea has become a microcosm of broader strategic rivalries, with external actors competing for dominance over this crucial maritime corridor. The United States, which has long maintained a military presence in the region, aims to ensure the security of key shipping lanes and maintain its influence in the Middle East. The U.S. Navy's 5th Fleet, based in Bahrain, regularly patrols the Red Sea and the Gulf of Aden, ensuring that vital maritime routes remain open and protected from threats such as terrorism and piracy.

On the other hand, China has increasingly asserted its presence in the Red Sea as part of its global Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). Through investments in infrastructure, ports, and trade routes, China aims to secure its supply chains and expand its influence. China's military base in Djibouti, its first overseas military installation, is a significant development in this regard. This base provides China with a foothold in the Red Sea, enabling it to protect its commercial interests and exert military influence in the broader Middle East and Africa. This move signals China's growing ambitions in the region and is seen as part of its broader strategy to challenge U.S. dominance in global geopolitics.

Iran's involvement in the region, particularly its support for proxy groups such as the Houthis, further complicates the geopolitical landscape. By supporting the Houthis, Iran seeks to counterbalance Saudi Arabia and extend its influence across the Arabian Peninsula. Iran's proxy strategy allows it to exert pressure on Saudi Arabia while projecting power in the Red Sea, without directly engaging in conflict. This form of asymmetric warfare has proven effective in destabilizing Saudi interests in Yemen, contributing to a broader pattern of rivalry between Iran and Saudi Arabia, which has implications for the entire Middle East.

Lastly, the Red Sea crisis and the Yemen War are not merely regional issues but part of a broader geopolitical struggle involving both regional and global actors. The competition for influence, resources, and strategic positions in this area has far-reaching consequences for international trade, energy security, and the balance of power in the Middle East and beyond. The involvement of major powers like the U.S. and China, alongside regional players such as Saudi Arabia, the UAE, and Iran, points to the growing significance of the Red Sea in global geopolitics, where economic interests and strategic rivalries are deeply intertwined.

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